

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE LITERARY ENVIRONMENT OF KASHKADARYA OASIS IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE.

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Abstract: This article describes the history of the literary environment of the Kashkadarya oasis and the stages of its development. The literary environment and its trends that emerged after independence are analyzed. A brief analysis of literary and fictional literature on the history of the oasis is also given. It has been considered that during the many thousand years of history of mankind, fiction has always accompanied him, and that this field has developed significantly in the years of independence.

The history of Uzbek literature and its development covers a very long period. If we analyze it from a historical point of view, at the beginning of the 20th century, our national literature entered the stage of extremely strong development.

During the years of independence, as in all fields, some positive work was done to revive the history of historical literature and the literary environment, and this is still going on. There is no doubt that the further development of the literary process in the regions will serve as a good impetus for the development of the literature of Uzbekistan in the future[1:5].

If we look at the history of literature, we can be sure that Kashkadarya also has a unique and large-scale, significant literary environment. It is known that the fate of many nobles and famous poets is closely connected with the soil of Kashkadarya oasis Nasaf and Kesh[2]. Hundreds of poets, scientists, even poets created under the pseudonym Nasafi [1:5]. Kashkadarya has long been a center of knowledge and enlightenment, a place of scientists, poets, and famous scholars.

The second half of the 20th century was the period of the rise of the literary environment of Kashkadarya and the enrichment of new artists: Gulshani, Togay Shoir, Shomurod Bakhshi, Suvon Soqi, Samar Nur, Azim (Bakhshi) Khojaev, Kadir (Bakhshi) Rahimov, Abdulla Oripov, Ikram Otamurodov, The scientific and artistic works of poets, writers and scientists such as Jumanyoz Jabbarov, Normurod Narzullaev, Ismail Tokhtamyshev[3], Khosiyat Lutfullaeva, Muhammad Achil, Jumaqul Qurban, Normurod Norqabil, Poyon Ravshanov, Ubaydulla Uvatov, Yusuf Berdiev made a worthy contribution to the development of literature. In the early 90s of the 20th century, Nazar Eshonqul, Chori Avaz, Amir Khudoyberdi, Zebo Mirzaeva, Habib

Abdunazar, Luqman Borikhan, Salim Ashur, Amirqul Karim, Ghulam Mirza and others were active poets and writers. During the years of independence[4:1492-1495], the literary life in the Kashkadarya oasis developed further. Achievements achieved during this period include Poyon Ravshanov's 4-volume selection on the history of ancient Nakhab and Kesh, Abdulla Oripov's Mirror of Justice, Koztumor, Normurod Narzullaev's Alyor, Ikram Otamurod's Taurus, Amir Khudoyberdi's "Ettinchi Malak", Habib Abdunazar's " [5:135-138] works such as Anjir guli" should be mentioned.

By the 20th century, another great poet - Abdulla Oripov - emerged from the land of Kashkadarya. It should be acknowledged separately[6:1-6] that a poet like Abdulla Oripov is born once in a hundred years. The most beautiful features of the ancient Uzbek poetry were embodied in the unique poems of the sensitive poet's heart. He has rightfully become an artist who is a symbol of Uzbek. He was highly respected as the Hero of Uzbekistan, People's Poet[7:96-100]. Today, in our region, large-scale works aimed at the literaryization of the poet's work are being carried out. An example of this is the measures aimed at the wider explanation of the poet's poetry and creativity to the young generation under the leadership of the head of our state. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 19, 2021 PQ-5188[2] is an example of this. According to this decision, the creative school named after Abdulla Oripov (specialized in native language and literature) started its activity in the center of Karshi city. From the day of establishment [8:121-123], the school has been providing education and training to boys and girls who are fond of literature and poetry.

"I am always proud to be a close friend of our hero poet Abdulla Oripov, who was born and raised in Kashkadarya, and a true admirer of his work[9:128-131]. Our great poet said: "You are a Kashkadaryom who has finished with Ptolemy", and he had endless respect for his native land. Frankly, I miss people like Abdulla Oripov today. He was very proud of Kashkadarya and loved his country. We organized meetings of young artists in Zamin with brother Abdulla, and the school of artists in Zamin became a tradition [10:128-132]. I recently made a proposal to open the Abdulla Oripov Museum in America at a meeting with US congressmen who were guests. They said they would help with that. You know, brother Abdullah died in the USA. Now, if we establish a good museum in that country, it would be a worthy thing for the memory of that person. If we are lucky, we will go to America and open this museum" [3] - said President Shavkat Mirziyoev.

In 2021, a presidential decision was made to widely celebrate the 80th anniversary of the birth of the Hero of Uzbekistan, People's Poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla

Oripov. A working group was established under the leadership of the Prime Minister of the Republic [12] and extensive celebrations of the 80th anniversary of the poet's birth were carried out on a national scale. According to the decision, on the third ten days of March 2021, a solemn literary and artistic memorial evening dedicated to the memory of Abdulla Oripov will be held at the Palace of International Conferences of Uzbekistan;

Preparing and publishing the two-volume "Selected works" of Abdulla Oripov in Uzbek, poetry collections translated into Karakalpak, Russian, English and other [13:59-63] languages, as well as the book "In memory of Abdullah Oripov's contemporaries";

Holding an international scientific-theoretical conference on the topic "The role of Abdullah Oripov's creative heritage in the development of Uzbek and world literary-aesthetic thinking" at the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi and publishing the materials of the conference as a separate collection [14:86-90];

Installation of a memorial plaque in the house where Abdulla Oripov lived in Arg'in neighborhood, Kibrai district, Tashkent region;

Work such as making a documentary film about the life and creative activity of Abdulla Oripov has been carried out.

Following in the footsteps of Abdulla Oripov, there are hundreds of poets and writers in Kashkadarya who have been and continue to work tirelessly to enrich the treasure of our literature, and the number of creative people [15:386-391] is increasing, and new talents are joining their ranks. During the period of independence, especially in the later period, the attention to the book increased even more, raising the culture of reading, improving the work of book publishing, organizing the avenue of poets in the greenest park of our capital, caring for the creative people [16:292-296], identifying young talents and encouraging them to create. creation of all necessary conditions is under the personal attention of President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev All these concerns are important for the further development of our fiction.

In the historic decision of the President "On measures to further improve the activities of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan" [18], it is stated that "to ensure the vital interests of the members of the Writers' Union, to adequately appreciate their hard creative work, which is of incomparable importance for the development of society, to develop the literature and art in all aspects , to strengthen the role and influence of the people of artistic creativity in the life of our society" [19] is not without reason.

The implementation of the tasks defined in the Decree "On the establishment of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting book reading and reading culture" [20] is also a program for raising the reading culture to a new level. Discovering and introducing to the people the true creators who are advancing tirelessly on the arduous paths of literature, objectively analyzing their works, giving them a proper assessment, and encouraging the people of creativity [17:26-28] to new achievements serve to enrich and elevate our spirituality. This can be clearly seen in the example of the achievements of artists from Kashkadarya. With the initiative of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and the support of the Kashkadarya regional administration, the book "Kashkadarya Writers" was prepared for publication by B. Yoldoshev. In this book, the literary environment of Kashkadarya, its ancient history, today and tomorrow are discussed in detail, the works of famous artists are analyzed, and their creative achievements and shortcomings are also discussed. It is distinguished by the methodological and formal researches of the creators, the bold illumination of our historical past and the broad illumination of the processes of deep penetration into the problems of current life.

In conclusion, as the Hero of Uzbekistan, the well-known literary scholar Ozod Sharafiddinov specially noted: "We will not fully understand the national literature of all Uzbeks without deeply analyzing and deeply studying the literary environment of each province of our republic, just like the rivers join together to form a river." There are sufficient conditions for the development of this industry in the Kashkadarya oasis.

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